

ABSTRACT BOOK

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TABLE OF CONTENT / SADRŽAJ

KEYNOTE PLENARY LECTURE		
ENVIRONMENT AND HEALTH IMPACT ASSESSMENT M. Martuzzi.	11	ANKETIRANJE STANOVNIŠTVA O UZNEMIRENOSTI BUKOM IZ ŽIVOTNE SREDINE U NOVOM SADU, 2006-2017 Emil Živadinovic, Sanja Bijelovic, Marija Jevtić, Nataša Dragic, Živojin Lalović, Siniša Milošević.
ENVIRONMENT AND HEALTH		
INVITED LECTURES		
ENVIRONMENTAL TOBACCO SMOKE AND HEALTH – RECENT ADVANCES IN RESEARCH Lubica Argalášová	15	PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVE SUBSTANCES IN THE WATER SUPPLY SYSTEM OF URBAN ECOSYSTEM Vesna Viher Hrženjak, M.D.
I THINK WHAT I BREATHE: AIR POLLUTION AND COGNITIVE DISORDERS Aleksandra Živković and Holger Stark	16	CONCENTRATION OF NITRATES IN PUBLIC WATER SYSTEMS AND GASTROINTESTINAL CANCER INCIDENCE IN THE MUNICIPALITIES OF BOGATIĆ AND LJUBOVIJA Igor Dragičević, Marijana Srećković, Dušan Backović, Jelena Ivetić, Vesna Lazić, Ljubica Pajić Nikolić, Slobodanka Bogdanović Vasić, Bojan Damnjanović
WHO ENVIRONMENTAL NOISE GUIDELINES FOR THE EUROPEAN REGION ± WHAT IS SCIENTIFIC NOVELTY? Prof. dr Goran Belojević, Full Professor	17	PITCH POSTER PRESENTATIONS HEALTH SAFETY OF DRINKING WATER IN THE UNA-SANA CANTON AREA DURING A FIVE-YEAR PERIOD (2014-2018) Jasmina Cepić
SPECIFICS AND PERSPECTIVES OF MONITORING THE IMPACT OF INDUSTRIALLY CONTAMINATED SITES ON THE ENVIRONMENT AND HEALTH OF THE POPULATION Aleksandar Corac.	21	OVERVIEW OF DRINKING WATER QUALITY ON PUBLIC TAPS AND FOUNTAINS WITH NATURAL WATER IN THE CITY OF BELGRADE IN 2018 Avramović D. Dušan, Ristanović-Ponjavić I., Zdravković S., Paunović N.
СПЕЦИФИЧНОСТИ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЕ ПРАЋЕЊА УТИЦАЈА ИНДУСТРИЈСКИ ЗАГАЂЕНИХ ПОДРУЧЈА НА ЖИВОТНУ СРЕДИНУ И ЗДРАВЉЕ СТАНОВНИШТВА Александар Ђорац	22	VINYL CHLORIDE – A NEW CHALLENGE FOR DRINKING WATER QUALITY IN SOME BELGRADE WATERWORKS Ristanović-Ponjavić Ivana, Avramović D., Pajić D., Zdravković S., Paunović N.
DRINKING-WATER AND HEALTH – RECENT ADVANCES IN RESEARCH Sanja Bijelovic, Dušica Stojanović	23	MONITORING OF LEGIONELLA IN SWIMMING POOLS WATER IN MONTENEGRO I. Joksimović, Z. Đorđević, B. Bajić, E. Kujundžić, S. Miladinović, M. Vujošević, Lj. Terić
MEDICAL WASTE – KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDES OF MEDICAL STUDENTS AND DOCTORS Jelena Ilić Živojinović	24	AIR QUALITY MONITORING SYSTEM UNDER THE AUTHORITY OF THE LOCAL SELF-GOVERNMENT UNIT OF THE CITY OF NOVI SAD Elma Bjelica, Dragica Branković.
ORAL PRESENTATIONS		
EXPOSURE TO INDOOR AIR POLLUTION AND ABSENTEEISM SCHOOLCHILDREN Ljiljana Stošić, Dušica Stojanović, Konstansa Lazarević	25	CONCENTRATION OF SOOT AND GENERAL PRACTITIONER VISITS FOR RESPIRATORY DISEASE Danijela Ilić, Ćorac A, Jović J, Mirković M, Milošević J ¹ , Đurić S, Bukumirić Z.
ENVIRONMENTAL NOISE ANNOYANCE OF THE POPULATION OF NOVI SAD FOR THE PERIOD 2006-2017 Emil Živadinovic, Sanja Bijelovic, Marija Jevtić, Nataša Dragic, Živojin Lalović, Siniša Milošević.	25	TECHNICAL AND LEGAL LIMITATIONS OF SPECIFIC SOURCE NOISE MEASUREMENT AND CONTROL Milan Konatarević dipl. inž. zašt. živ. sred., dr Slaviša Mladenović spec. hig., dr Dragan Pajić spec. hig.

VIDEO PRESENTATIONS (PPT)	ORAL PRESENTATIONS
DETECTION OF NITROGEN OXIDES IN VALJEVO AND THEIR IMPORTANCE FOR HUMAN HEALTH AND VEGETATION Dr Snežana Pakić, dr Đorđe Vuković..... 33	INFLUENCE OF FAMILY AND SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT ON CHILDREN'S HEALTHY CHOICES Enisa Kujundzic 47
DETECTION OF SO ₂ IN VALJEVO AND ITS IMPORTANCE FOR HUMAN HEALTH AND VEGETATION Dr Đorđe Vuković, dr Snežana Pakić..... 33	PARENTAL INFLUENCE ON THE RISK OF OBESITY AT 7 YEAR OLD CHILDREN Vesna Bilić-Kirin, Angelina Paić, Vesna Buljan, Ines Banjari..... 47
AIR QUALITY IN NIS FROM 2011–2018 THROUGH THE MONITORED FRACTIONS OF SUSPENDED PM 10 PARTICLES Biljana Ljubenovic, Jelena Ciric 34	HAVING A PET AS A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE Sara Savić, Marina Žekić Stošić, Doroteja Marčić, Marija Jevtić 48
SAFETY OF RURAL WATER SUPPLY IN THE PIROT DISTRICT FOR THE PERIOD 2014–2018 Jovanović Miloš, Stanković Z., Vidanović T..... 34	PITCH POSTER PRESENTATIONS
SOIL CONTAMINATION TESTING WITHIN WATER SUPPLY PROTECTED AREAS ON THE TERRITORY OF BELGRADE L. Ivančajić, D. Pajić, S.Mladenović, V. Slepčević..... 35	THE ATTITUDES OF TYPICAL STUDENTS TO CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES IN 2012 AND 2017 Jasmina Radojlovic, Snezana Jesic Gojak..... 49
SEASONAL DYNAMICS OF POLLEN AND NON-SPECIFIC POLLUTION IN THE AIR OF PANČEVO Nikolovski Dubravka, Trajkovska Gabrijela, Mičić Danijela, Đurić Snežana..... 35	KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE, AND PRACTICE TOWARD ORAL HEALTH AMONG PHARMACIST IN FEDERATION BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA Milka Dančević-Gojković, MD and Elma Sokić-Begović, DS 49
PHYSICO-CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF BOTTLED NATURAL MINERAL WATERS IN SALES Jelena Videnovic, J. Čirić..... 36	WALKING AS A PHYSICAL ACTIVITY IN THE CITY OF ZAGREB-EHIS 2014/2015 Puljak A., Živec M., Marić Bajš M., Polić-Vižintin M. 50
CONTAMINATED SITES AND POTENTIAL RISKS TO HUMAN HEALTH AND ENVIRONMENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA Milan Milutinović, Dragan Crnković, Andrej Šoštarić, Dragana Vidojević, Nemanja Jevtić, Aleksandra Šiljić-Tomić 36	SMOKING PREVALENCE OF EMPLOYEES IN HEALTH CARE INSTITUTIONS IN BELGRADE Mr sc. med. dr Anđelija Nešković, dr Gordana Belamarić, dr Mladen Babić, dr Vladimir Miletić.... 50
IMPROVING OF AMBIENT AIR QUALITY MONITORING NETWORKS FOR ASSESSING POPULATION EXPOSURE AND POTENTIAL HEALTH IMPACT Nataša Dragic, Sanja Bijelovic, Emil Živadinovic 37	VIDEO PRESENTATIONS (PPT)
HEALTHY LIFESTYLE	LIFE HABITS AMONG STUDENTS IN NOVI SAD Branislava Teofilović, Dušica Rakić, Ljiljana Suvajdžić, Emilia Gligorić, Aleksandar Takači, Nevena Grujić Letić..... 51
INVITED LECTURES	GENDER DIFFERENCES IN RISK FACTORS FOR TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS Nela Djonovic, Dalibor Stajic, Dragan Vasiljevic, Milos Stepovic, Marija Sekulic 51
PUBLIC HEALTH: ACHIEVEMENTS AND CHALLENGES IN A GLOBALISED PERSPECTIVE Gianfranco Damiani ^{1,2} 41	ADOLESCENTS' SUN BEHAVIOR Suzana Miljković 52
EDCS PREVENTIVE MEDICINE AND PUBLIC HEALTH IMPLICATIONS VS LONGEVITY Evangelos A Polychronopoulos..... 42	ADVERSE CHILDHOOD EXPERIENCES AND MENTAL HEALTH SERVICES USE – RETROSPECTIVE ANALYSIS ON THE STUDENT POPULATION – dr Milena Jakovljević, prof. dr Bojana Matejić, dr Aleksandar Medarević 52
INDIVIDUAL CHOICES IN THE LIGHT OF SDGS AND GLOBAL CHALLENGES Marija Jevtic, MD, PhD, Full professor..... 43	THE FREQUENCY OF HYPERTENSION AMONG PATIENTS OF THE HEALTH CENTRE NOVI SAD dr Tatjana Zdravković, prim. dr Tatjana Egić, dr Gordana Tomin Petrović..... 53
PROMOTING HEALTHY LIFESTYLES IN THE WORKING ENVIROMENT: HEALTHY COMPANY Assoc.Prof. Danijela Štimac Grbić, MD, PhD 44	RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TELEVISION WATCHING AND OVERWEIGHT AND OBESITY IN ADOLESCENTS Nikolina Banjanin, Nikola Banjanin 53
NUTRITION THROUGH THE LIFE CYCLE: FROM CHILDHOOD TO THE ELDERLY YEARS Assistant professor Dragana Stojisavljević..... 45	DEPICTION OF AVERAGE FOOD SUPPLEMENTS USER IN SERBIA Suzana Miljković, Jasmina Radojlović 54

PROGRAM „JAČANJE KOMPETENCIJA U RADU S MLADIMA“ Snježana Šalamon, Andreja Radić, Lucija Sabljć, Mirjana Orban	54	MALIGNANT DISEASE CONTROL – PREVENTION, ORGANIZED SCREENING RESULTS AND ORGANIZED CANCER SCREENING PROGRAM Jovanović Verica	65
PROGRAMME „COMPETENCE STRENGTHENING IN WORKING WITH YOUTH“ Snježana Šalamon, Andreja Radić, Lucija Sabljć, Mirjana Orban	55	SURVEY ON HIV-RELATED KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDES AND PRACTICE OF HEALTH CARE WORKERS Full Prof. Biljana Kocić	66
THE INCIDENCE OF BURNOUT AMONG CRITICAL CARE NURSES: A SHORT CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY Dejan Živanović, Jovan Matijašević, Svetlana Stojkov Jovan Javorac	55	OUTCOMES OF THE PREVENTIVE PROGRAMS IN TUZLA CANTON Mulić M.	67
EATING KNOWLEDGE AND BEHAVIOUR OF FIRST GRADE PUPILS Jelena Bjelanovic, Popovic Milka, Velicki Radmila. . .	56	ORAL PRESENTATIONS	
CORRELATION BETWEEN THE SCHOOL URBANIZATION GRADE AND OVERWEIGHT AND OBESITY IN 7 YEARS OLD CHILDREN IN MONTENEGRO E. Kujundzic, I. Joksimovic, B. Bajić, Z. Đorđević, M. Vujošević	56	MENTALNO ZDRAVLJE I PREVENCIJA DEPRESIVNOSTI I ANKSIOZNOSTI KOD STUDENTSKE POPULACIJE Ivana Simić Vukomanović, doc.dr. Ivana Simić Vukomanović	69
OBESITY AND EATING HABITS IN SCHOOL AGE CHILDREN Durmišević J., Durmišević-Serdarević J., Durmišević S.	57	MENTAL HEALTH AND PREVENTION OF DEPRESSIVE AND ANXIETY SYMPTOMS OF THE STUDENT POPULATION Ivana Simić Vukomanović.	69
QUALITY LIFE IMPROVEMENT OF PERSONS WITH INTELLECTUAL DISABILITIES THROUGHOUT HEALTH PROMOTION INTERVENTIONS Škes M, Lukavečki V, Kliček M	57	TRENDS IN THE UTILIZATION OF ANTIPSYCHOTIC DRUGS IN ZAGREB-CROATIA: IMPROVEMENT IN PRIMARY HEALTH CARE PRESCRIBING PATTERNS? Marina Polić-Vižintin and Zvonimir Šostar	70
PROGRAM IMPLEMENTATION OF PREVENTIVE EXAMINATIONS IN FAMILY MEDICINE IN ZAGREB Maric-Bajs M, Puljak A, Polic Vizintin M.	58	THE POSITIVE INFLUENCE OF THE NON-INSTITUTIONAL FORM OF ORGANIZING OF OLD PEOPLE ON THEIR PHYSICAL AND MENTAL HEALTH M. Sarihodžić, S. Azabagić, L. Hasanović	70
IS THE ASSOCIATION BETWEEN SELF-RATED HEALTH AND OBESITY DIFFERENT FOR MEN AND WOMEN IN VOJVODINA? Ivana Radić, Mirjana Martinov Cvejin, Sanja Harhaji, Vesna Mijatović Jovanović, Dragana Milijašević, Tanja Tomašević	58	PITCH POSTER PRESENTATIONS	
THE ASSOCIATION BETWEEN DEPRESSION AND PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AMONG POPULATION IN VOJVODINA Sanja Harhaji, Ivana Radić, Nataša Dragnić, Svetlana Kvirgić, Vesna Mijatović Jovanović, Sonja Čanković .	59	ADDRESSING REFUGEE HEALTH THROUGH EVIDENCE-BASED PRACTICE: A CASE STUDY FROM TURKEY – THE CHALLENGES IN PROVIDING HEALTH CARE TO SYRIAN REFUGEES Melita Petanović, MD, Senior M&E Expert	73
SPORTS ACTIVITIES IN RELATION TO THE SMOKING, ALCOHOL, COFFEE AND ENERGETIC DRINKS CONSUMPTION, AMONG ADOLESCENTS IN SERBIA Jović Jelena, Aleksandar Ćorac, Danijela Ilić, Goran Trajković, Zoran Bukumirić, Dragana Ignjatović Ristić	59	100 YEARS SINCE SPANISH FLU – WHAT DO WE LEARN? THE ROLE OF FAMILY DOCTORS IN INFECTION DISEASE'S PREVENTION Dorica Sandutu, Sandra Alexiu, Cristina Barbu, Ioana Budiu, Anca Deleanu, Gindrovel Dumitra, Maria Lup, Dana Popescu, Daniela Stefanescu, Madalina Vesa, Cosmina Berbecel.	73
		PREDICTORS OF MUSCULOSKELETAL PAIN IN SCHOOL CHILDREN IN BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA: GENDER DIFFERENCES Selma Azabagić, Nurka Pranjić	74
		LET'S TALK ABOUT THE MENTAL HEALTH OF IMMIGRANTS IN THE CITY OF ZAGREB Boris Gracin, Danica Romac, Mirjana Orban, Zrinka Čavar	74
DISEASE PREVENTION		VIDEO PRESENTATIONS (PPT)	
INVITED LECTURES		PREVENTION AND RATIONAL TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH A BACK PAIN Prim. MD Danijel Atijas, MD.Ph.D. Suzana Savić, MD. Ph.D. Draško Kuprešak	77
DISEASE PREVENTION AMONG SCHOOL CHILDREN prof. dr. Nela Đonović	63	ETIOLOGY OF BALKAN ENDEMIC NEPHROPATHY: HISTORICAL REVIEW Ana Jovanović, Danka Đorović, Ljiljana Bogdanović	77
SCREENINGS IN MONTENEGRO – NECESSITY AND CHALLENGE B. Mugoša	64		

RELATIONSHIPS OF THE BODY MASS INDEX AND THE RELAXATION MODEL OF YOUNG PEOPLE Liljana Sokolova, Dusko Simić, Veselin Bunčić, Svetlana Stojkov	78	SECONDARY PREVENTION OF RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS BY APPLYING DIFFERENT DIETS Dragan Vasiljević, Mirjana Veselinović, Vladimir Jakovljević, Nela Đonović, Mirjana Milosavljević, Snežana Radovanović.	92
PROPER NUTRITION WITH PHYSICAL ACTIVITY- THE ROAD TO HEALTH PRESERVATION Đurović Ljiljana,	78	ORAL PRESENTATIONS	
IMPROVING THE COOPERATION BETWEEN THE FAMILY DOCTOR AND THE PATRONAGE NURSE Dragica A. Shuleva	79	FOOD FRAUD – RISK TO ASSESS Dragana Jovic	93
VIOLENCE AS A FORM OF INDIVIDUAL AND GROUP BEHAVIOR Dragica Šuleva	79	PESTICIDES IN PLANT FOOD FOR INFANTS IN SERBIA – WHERE ARE WE? Vesna Pantić-Palibrk, Maja Ristić, Stefanija Opalić, Dunja Koprivica, Milijana Stepanović, Gorica Vuković, Nebojša Vuković, Vladimir Nikolić	93
MULTIDISCIPLINARY TEAMWORK – NURSE IN PUBLIC HEALTH Matea Živec, RN, BSN, MSN, Cecilija Rotim, RN, BSN, MS. MSN, PhD(s)	80	PITCH POSTER PRESENTATIONS	
PREVALENCE OF CHRONIC NON-COMMUNICABLE DISEASES AND ASSOCIATED FACTORS AMONG OLDER ADULTS Snežana Radovanović, Sanja Kocić, Svetlana Radević, Ivana Simić Vukomanović, Dragan Vasiljević, Nela Đonović.	81	DETERMINATION OF CANNABINOIDS IN HEMP-BASED FOOD PRODUCTS Nebojša Kladar, Branislava Srdenović Čonić, Neda Gavarić, Nebojša Salaj, Biljana Božin, Ljilja Torović	95
SOCIOECONOMIC INEQUALITIES IN THE USE HEALTH CARE FOR WOMEN RELATED TO REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH Snežana Radovanović, Sanja Kocić, Svetlana Radević, Dragan Vasiljević, Nataša Mihailović, Katarina Janičijević	81	RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN NUTRITIONAL STATUS AND SEVERITY OF CORONARY DISEASE Tijana Dangubić, Petar Otašević, Marina Nikić, Jadranka Maksimović, Nadja Vasiljević, Djordje Radak, Miloš Maksimović	95
GENDER DIFFERENCES IN RISK FACTORS FOR TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS Nela Djonovic, Dalibor Stajic, Dragan Vasiljevic, Milos Stepovic, Marija Sekulic	82	MEDITERRANEAN DIET AND ACUTE CORONARY SYNDROME Velicki R, Popovic M, Petrovic M, Bjelanovic J	96
EARLY TREATMENT OF DEPRESSION AS PREVENTION FOR DEMENTIA Marija Kušan Jukić	82	VIDEO PRESENTATIONS (PPT)	
HAND HYGIENE PRACTICES OF FOOD HANDLERS IN MONTENEGRO Snezana Barjaktarovic-Labovic, Boban Mugosa, Gorica Sbutega Milošević, Maja Nikolić, Vesna Andrejević	83	TOXICITY RISK ASSESSMENT OF ELEMENTS IN SYRUPS INTENDED FOR PEDIATRIC POPULATION Lukić Danijela, Srdjenović-Čonić B., Velicki R., Popović M., Bijelović S., Torović Lj	97
RELATIONS OF BODY COMPOSITION AND MAXIMAL EXPLOSIVE MUSCLE FORCE OBTAINED BY HAND GRIP MEASUREMENT IN FEMALE STUDENTS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF BELGRADE Đorđević-Nikić M., Dopsaj M., Popović A., Dopsaj V., Marković S.	83	CHEMICAL HAZARDS IN FOOD – “COUNTRY OF ORIGIN” SERBIA ON THE RAPID ALERT SYSTEM FOR FOOD AND FEED (RASFF) Ljilja Torović, Vera Gusman, Radmila Velicki, Milka Popović, Sanja Bijelović	97
EPILEPSY IN THE PRIMARY HEALTH CARE ORDINATION Mirza Kadic, Sabina Catic, Marina Kljajevic	84	BIOGENIC AMINES IN ARTISANAL DRY FERMENTED SAUSAGES AND ASSOCIATED HEALTH RISK FOR CONSUMERS Ljilja Torović, Vera Gusman, Radmila Velicki, Milka Popović, Sanja Bijelović	98
FOOD, NUTRITION AND HEALTH		PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING OF BARK AND LEAF EXTRACTS OF SALIX FRAGILIS L. Emilia Gligorić, Ružica Igić, Ljiljana Suvajdžić, Branislava Teofilović, Nevena Grujić-Letić.	98
INVITED LECTURES		HEALTH RISK ASSESSMENT FOR PEDIATRIC POPULATION ASSOCIATED WITH ETHANOL AND SELECTED RESIDUAL SOLVENTS IN HERBAL BASED PRODUCTS Nebojša Kladar, Branislava Srdenović Čonić, Ljilja Torović, Biljana Božin, Nebojša Salaj, Jan Sudi	99
NUTRITION POLICY OF BULGARIA Prof. Vesselka Laleva Duleva, MD, PhD.	87	ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY AND PRELIMINARY CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF COMMERCIAL TEA SAMPLES (<i>CAMELLIA SINENSIS</i> L.) Emilia Gligorić, Ružica Igić, Ljiljana Suvajdžić, Branislava Teofilović, Nevena Grujić-Letić.	99
DIETARY INFLAMMATORY INDEX: A NEW TOOL FOR ASSESSMENT DIET QUALITY BASED ON INFLAMMATORY POTENTIAL Sonja Radaković.	88	HERBAL FOOD SAFETY IN NIŠAVA AND TOPLICA DISTRICT Jelena Čirić	100

PARTICIPATION OF ALTERNATIVE MODES OF NUTRITION AMONG YOUNG SOCCER PLAYERS IN SUBOTICA Liljana Sokolova, Ivan Katančić, Dejan Živanović, Nenad Đokić	100	NUTRITION IN THE CONTROL OF TYPE 2 DIABETES Hajnalka Požar	108
HEALTH CONCERNS RELATED TO TATTOO INKS ON THE RAPID ALERT SYSTEM FOR NON-FOOD CONSUMER PRODUCTS (RAPEX) G. Milojević-Miodragović, Lj. Torović	101	SUGAR PROFILE OF HONEYS FROM SERBIA Milica Živkov Baloš, Sandra Jakšić, Željko Mihaljev, Nenad Popov, Dragana Ljubojević Pelić, Suzana Vidaković	108
HEALTH RISKS ASSOCIATED WITH TATTOO AND PMU PRODUCTS Vesna Viher Hrženjak, M.D., public health specialist	101	LABELING OF HONEY AND HONEYBEE MIXTURES, RESTRICTIONS AND DANGERS OF ADDITION OF SOME INGREDIENTS Lasić Dario	109
THE CONTENT OF PHTHALATES IN TOYS IN THE REPUBLIC OF SRPSKA FROM 2016 TO 2018 Vesna Lazić, Miodrag Marjanović, Vesna Petković, Vesna Rudić Grujić, Milena Todorović	102	NUTRITION RISK SCREENING AMONG PRESCHOOLERS Karolina Berenji, Sandra Vujkov, Zoran Milić, Milenko Janković	109
PERSONAL HYGIENE PRODUCTS SAFETY AND FACE AND BODY PRODUCTS SAFETY IN NIŠ DISTRICT Jelena Ćirić	102	OBESITY AND EATING DISORDER COUNSELLING AT ZAGREB YOUTH HEALTH CENTER Petričević N, Miletić Ćinić L.	110
SUGAR AND CARBOHYDRATES INTAKE AND CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE RISK IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN Stojanovic Dusica, Lazarevic Konstansa, Stošić Ljiljana	103	NUTRITION AND SUPPLEMENTATION OF YOUNG ATHLETE Radmila Jovanovic	110
RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MAGNESIUM DEFICIENCY AND ADVERSE CONDITIONS IN PREGNANCY Nikola Banjanin, Nikolina Banjanin	103	DIETARY PROTEIN AND PHOSPHORUS INTAKE IN HEMODIALYSIS PATIENTS Slavica Raden, Danijela Ristić Medić, Nela Popović, Brankica Terzić, Mirjana Mijušković	111
IDENTIFICATION AND ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE OF ENTEROBACTERIACEAE IN FOOD Lekić J., Gusman V., Pavlović G., Zivlak B., Popović M., Bijelović S.	104	HYGIENIC-DIETARY REGIME DURING HOMEOPATHY TREATMENT Ljiljana Bajić Bibić	111
MICROBIOLOGICAL HAZARDS IN FOOD – “COUNTRY OF ORIGIN” SERBIA ON THE RAPID ALERT SYSTEM FOR FOOD AND FEED (RASFF) Jelena Lekić, Vera Gusman, Radmila Velicki, Milka Popović, Sanja Bijelović, Ljilja Torović	104	ARSENIC LEVELS IN RICE-BASED INFANT FOOD – CONCERN, YES OR NO? Maja Ristić, Vesna Pantić-Palibrk, Stefanija Opalić, Dunja Koprivica, Milijana Stepanović	111
DETECTION OF <i>SALMONELLA</i> SPP. IN FOOD SAMPLES USING MSRV AGAR Gusman V., Lekić J., Medić D., Pavlović G., Bijelović S., Popović M.	105	SALT CONTENT IN DEHYDRATED SOUPS RETAILED IN NOVI SAD, SERBIA Popović M, Torović Lj, Velicki R, Červenka I, Lukić D, Bjelanović J, Bijelović S	112
MICROBIOLOGICAL PROFILE OF DRY FERMENTED SAUSAGES FROM ARTISANAL PRODUCTION Vera Gusman, Jelena Lekić, Radmila Velicki, Milka Popović, Sanja Bijelović, Ljilja Torović	105	CLAIMS ON FOOD SUPPLEMENTS – CHALLENGES IN MONTENEGRO Borko Bajić, Zorica Đorđević, Ivana Joksimović, Dijana Đurović	112
PREVENTIVE MICROBIOLOGICAL CONTROL IN SOUP KITCHEN PREMISES Dunja Koprivica, Vesna Pantić – Palibrk, Maja Ristić, Stefanija Opalić	106	ESCHERICHIA COLI IN TRADITIONALLY MADE DAIRY PRODUCTS IN MONTENEGRO Borko Bajić, Zorica Đorđević, Ljubica Terić, Dijana Đurović, Ivana Joksimović	113
IMPORTANCE OF DEHYDRATION IN MODERN SPORT Danka Djorovic, Ana Jovanovic, Milos Maksimovic.	106	AN OCCURRENCE OF <i>LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES</i> IN READY-TO-EAT MEAT PRODUCTS AND MEAT PROCESSING PLANTS IN MONTENEGRO Zorica Đorđević, Borko Bajić, Ljubica Terić, Sanja Medenica, Sandra Đurđević	113
CONSUMPTION PATTERNS OF FLUID INTAKE AMONG ADOLESCENTS AND YOUNG ADULTS IN SUBOTICA Karolina Berenji, Nataša Sabo Čamprag.	107	IODINE INTAKE OF PREGNANT WOMEN IN THE FRAMEWORK OF THE REDUCTION OF SALT INTAKE IN MONTENEGRO Z. Đorđević, B. Bajić, I. Joksimović, E. Kujundžić, S. Medenica	114
DIETARY HABITS AMONG STUDENTS IN NOVI SAD Branislava Teofilović, Dušica Rakić, Ljiljana Suvadžić, Emilia Gligorić, Aleksandar Takači, Nevena Grujić Letić	107	DETERMINATION OF FUMONISINS IN MEDICINAL PLANTS BY LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY Sandra Jakšić, Milica Živkov Baloš, Biljana Abramović	114
		LIST OF AUTHORS	116

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in obese children (4.78% vs 4.57%). As expected, obese children have the highest risk of cardiovascular comorbidities (observed as cardiometabolic risk, CMR and blood pressure), but children who sleep longer have lower BMI. Maternal pre-pregnancy weight correlates with child's BMI, but paternal BMI has higher influence on child's BMI. Employment and higher income correlate with lower BMI and CMR of a child. Maternal (p=0.037) and paternal smoking (p=0.019) correlate with higher BMI. Confirmed independent risks for child overweight and obesity are diastolic blood pressure (per each 1 mm Hg the risk increases by 11.9%),

maternal smoking (children who have non-smoking mothers have 68.8% lower risk), pre-pregnancy weight (the risk drops by 6.9% per each kg less), short sleep duration (44.6% higher risk) and family meals (the risk drops by 24.0% with more family meals).

CONCLUSION: The results are in line with what we know so far on the risks for child obesity but further emphasize father's role.

KEY WORDS: childhood obesity, nutritional status, parental influence, IOTF criteria

HAVING A PET AS A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE

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Nowadays, people became attached to their pets and some would even say too attached. The emotional level of connection with an animal, living in the same household, is so much higher than a century ago. Pets became actual members of the families, sharing the same space, bed, sofa or even plate! There is evidence that pets really do increase the quality of the owners life (adults or kids), but there are also some diseases or disorders that can jeopardize the health of the owner or the animal, due to this kind of relationship.

THE AIM of our work is to show the most important highlights of a pet-human relationship, good and bad, from One Health perspective. The method is a descriptive one from different studies done during the last 5 years. There are more or less dangerous diseases that can be

transferred from the pet to the owner, like rabies, scabies or even MRSA. There are disorders that can be "transferred" the other way around, from humans to animals like obesity or a habit of "not walking". But there are also zoonotic diseases that can equally threaten humans and animals at the same time and most often those are vector borne diseases like dirofilariosis, leishmaniasis, Lyme borreliosis.

TO CONCLUDE, the pets overall can increase the healthy lifestyle of humans, but humans need to be responsible for the health status and preventive measures for both – pets and humans.

KEY WORDS: One Health, vector borne diseases, pets, zoonotic diseases